

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<p>Internal attributes or resources that give an advantage over competitors</p> <p><i>(e.g., unique technology, skilled team, cost efficiency).</i></p>	<p>Internal limitations or challenges that may hinder success</p> <p><i>(e.g., limited market visibility, resource constraints, high production costs).</i></p>

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<p>External factors that can be leveraged to benefit the business or project</p> <p><i>(e.g., growing market demand, favorable regulations, new technology trends).</i></p>	<p>External factors that could pose risks or challenges</p> <p><i>(e.g., competition, economic instability, changing consumer preferences, loss of rights).</i></p>